

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

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MEASUREMENT-BASED CARE FOR DEPRESSION

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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By

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ABSTRACT

Measurement-based care (MBC) has not been widely adopted in behavioral health (BH), which is a requirement of a recently revised care, treatment, and services standard for accreditation in BH settings (The Joint Commission [TJC], 2017). The purpose of this quality improvement (QI) project was to develop, implement, and evaluate an MBC Depression Protocol using the Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9). This was implemented to monitor progress and assure compliance with regulatory requirements for safe, effective and measurable care for patients with major depressive disorder (MDD). In this study, a convenience sample of 44 BH personnel was educated and evaluated on a newly created “MBC of Depression Protocol at the St. Joseph Hospital of Orange.” De-identified PHQ-9 scores of MDD patients were analyzed, and protocol adherence by outpatient BH personnel was measured. In-service knowledge and confidence scores improved by approximately 32% (n=44). Protocol adherence by the outpatient staff met the target of 3 (100%) PHQ-9 surveys per patient. The mean aggregate change in PHQ-9 scores over episodes of care was 56% (n = 20) indicating a significant response to treatment. MBC will lead to improved patient-centric care by quantifying the outcomes of care, treatment, and services provided to patients. PHQ-9 monitoring may function as a “lab” test for depression.

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BACKGROUND

In behavioral health (BH) settings, a long-standing accreditation requirement of The Joint Commission (TJC) is compliance with the Care, Treatment, and Services (CTS) Standard CTS.03.01.09 (TJC, 2017). This standard assesses the outcomes of CTS provided to individual BH patients (TJC, 2017). The purpose of such an assessment is the evaluation and monitoring of an individual BH patient's clinical status and progress (TJC, 2017). The standard was revised in 2017 to require organizations to assess outcomes by using "a standardized tool or instrument" (TJC, 2017, p. 10). The goal of the revised standard is to help organizations improve the quality of care delivery via the use of tools to quantify progress (TJC, 2017). Lewis et al. (2019) describe BH measurement-based care (MBC) as "the systematic evaluation of patient symptoms before or during an encounter to inform BH treatment" (p. E1). The term "measurement-based care" (Trivedi et al., 2006, p. 29) has been increasingly used in BH literature over the last two decades and is also referred to as "routine outcomes monitoring," "measurement feedback system," "progress monitoring," and "patient-reported outcome measures" (Lewis, 2019; The Kennedy Forum, 2015; Scott & Lewis, 2015).

To demonstrate compliance with the revised standard, the following elements of performance are required: 1) use of "a standardized tool or instrument to monitor the individual's progress" in achieving CTS goals; 2) analysis of the data from the tool to inform and monitor the individual's goals and objectives as needed (the standard calls out specific requirements for organizations that provide eating disorders services); and 3) use of aggregate data from the standardized tool to improve organizational performance and to evaluate outcomes of the CTS to the population(s) served (TJC, 2017, p. 10). The tool

or instrument may focus on either or both of the following: a) a specific population or diagnostic category, e.g., depression or anxiety; or b) a more general assessment such as distress, functional status, or quality of life (TJC, 2017, p. 10).

As in primary care, which may use reliable and valid measures to inform treatment decisions, such as in patients with hypertension (blood pressure measurements) or diabetes (glucose laboratory values), MBC uses standardized instruments to quantify and inform BH services (Lewis et al., 2019). Healthcare organizations, such as health plans and medical groups, view MBC as a means to track behavioral “health vital signs” (Steinfeld, Franklin, Mercer, Fraynt, & Simon, 2016, p. 377). The benefits of MBC may include providing insight into treatment progress, highlighting ongoing treatment goals, reducing symptom deterioration, and improving client outcomes (Scott & Lewis, 2015).

Research shows that routine outcome monitoring (ROM) and feedback using standardized measurement tools improve patient outcomes, such as in the treatment of depression (Boswell, Constantino, Kraus, Bugatti & Oswald, 2016). In a study comparing MBC with standard care for patients with severe major depression lasting for six months, Guo et al. (2015) found MBC significantly more effective in achieving both response (86.9% versus 62.7%, $p=0.002$) and remission (73.8% vs. 28.8%, $p<0.001$), and the speed with which these two outcomes were achieved was also improved. MBC allows for customization of treatment decisions for individual patients, which in turn can demonstrate higher response rates and shorter times to remission; this may translate to reduced symptoms, relapse, suicide, and improved function (Guo et al., 2015). Providing more specific information about the symptoms of the patient allows more precise titration (Guo et al., 2015). Additionally, the incorporation of self-reported measures may improve

patients' engagement since they will monitor their own symptoms and side effects (Guo et al., 2015). The use of MBC improved patient satisfaction and focus on the visit by both the patient and clinician in a large integrated healthcare organization (Steinfeld et al., 2016).

Statement of the Problem

BH conditions, such as depression, anxiety, and substance abuse, are common and disabling disorders that often occur with chronic medical conditions, such as angina, asthma, and diabetes (Tuso, 2014). If the BH condition is inadequately treated, patients who also have comorbid medical disorders may have poorer health outcomes (Tuso, 2014). Over the last two decades, mental health disorders top the list of the costliest medical conditions, with the estimated cost for mental health diagnoses reaching \$201 billion in 2013, in contrast to \$147 billion spent on heart conditions (Roehrig, 2016).

Although both interest and research in MBC have grown over the last 20 years, fewer than 20% of BH clinicians have adopted its use (Lewis et al., 2019; Scott & Lewis, 2015). Since the inception of the revised CTS standard, a local hospital in southern California, with both inpatient and outpatient BH services, has been manually assessing and tracking outcomes on CTS. However, the hospital has not established an effective process for extracting the outcomes information. Although the hospital's leadership team has not identified any quality of care issues, management has been researching ways to meet the challenge of MBC optimally. Major depressive disorder (MDD) is highly prevalent, affecting about 7% of adults in the United States at any given time, and among the top three diagnoses nationwide and at this facility (American Psychiatric Association [APA], 2013, Siu et al., 2016). Moreover, it is among the leading causes of disability

(Pratt & Brody, 2014). Yet, despite the clinical importance of MDD, it is often inadequately treated (Wang et al., 2005). For these reasons, a protocol to implement MBC in this population is needed.

Purpose

The purpose of this project was to develop, implement, and evaluate a protocol for utilization of a standardized tool for patients with MDD to assure compliance with regulatory requirements for safe, effective, and measurable care. Aims of this project included the following: 1) review, analyze, and evaluate the literature for tools relevant to the MDD population(s) served; 2) recommend and select tool(s) based on evidence, stakeholder input, and feasibility; 3) develop and implement a protocol for utilization of the selected tool(s)/instrument(s); and 4) educate, train, and evaluate the knowledge and confidence level of site nurses in using the protocol. The clinical practice questions included the following:

1. What is the baseline knowledge of BHS staff regarding the revised CTS standard, MBC, depression assessment using PHQ-9, and the new protocol?
2. What is the impact of education and training on staff knowledge and confidence in using the revised CTS standard, MBC, PHQ-9, and protocol?
3. What is the adherence by the BHS staff to a new protocol as measured by the number of total PHQ-9 assessments for the MDD population?
4. What is the aggregate patient response of CTS, as measured by the change in PHQ-9 scores from admission to discharge over two months (monthly) as presented by:
 - a. Mean aggregate change in scores
 - b. Change in scores grouped in quartiles

Supporting Framework

Quality improvement (QI) is the systematic upgrading of care delivery, which is continuous, ongoing, and measurable to implement changes that lead to better patient outcomes and better system performance (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality, 2019; Batalden & Davidoff, 2007). QI aims to make healthcare safer, more efficient, patient-centered, timely, effective, and equitable (Donnelly & Kirk, 2015). The QI model for this project is the Plan, Do, Study, Act cycle.

Plan, Do, Study, Act

The Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) cycle, also known as the Deming Wheel, is a four-stage, iterative, systematic process focused on the continual improvement of a product, process, or service (Crowfoot & Prasad, 2017; The Deming Institute, 2019).

Plan

The planning phase includes understanding the problem and the background of why it is a problem, as well as describing the proposed solutions (Donnelly & Kirk, 2015). The planning phase includes identification of goals with details of how the plan is to be carried out, including collecting and evaluating the data and predicting the expected outcomes (Christoff, 2018; Donnelly & Kirk, 2015).

The principal goal of this project is for the relevant personnel in the BHS of this hospital to become knowledgeable and confident in using the selected standardized tools and protocol appropriately. This stage includes assessing the organization's current methods of measuring care for patients with depression, tool evaluation and selection, and protocol development. The predicted outcomes are that the BH staff will understand the selected tool, have confidence in using it, and use it per the protocol.

Do

In this stage, the plan is carried out with documentation of the relevant data to identify successes, issues, or unexpected outcomes (Christoff, 2018). It is essential to collect and measure data over some time so that patterns can be charted or displayed (Donnelly & Kirk, 2015). Rarely, improvement efforts go smoothly. Possible reasons for this are that the change may not be implemented properly, the support processes to make the change may be inadequate, or the results are not favorable even though the change is executed as planned. (Crowfoot & Prasad, 2017; Provost & Murray, 2011).

For this DNP project, implementation includes assessing nursing knowledge and confidence in using the selected standardized tool(s) and protocol. An education program will be developed and presented to the targeted BH (BH) personnel. Assessments will be collected at pre-education and post-education following in-service. These will be referred to as “pre-test” and “post-test.”

Study

In this stage, the data are analyzed, and the findings documented and discussed with the stakeholders. Based on findings, a decision is made as to whether the program has achieved its goals, and if the intervention should be adopted, adapted, or abandoned (Christoff, 2018; Crowfoot & Prasad, 2017). In this phase, the results are compared to those that were predicted. The results should also be compared to those of previous, relevant projects if any (Christoff, 2018; Institute for Healthcare Improvement, 2017).

The results of the pre- and post-testing of the nurses’ knowledge and confidence will be evaluated and discussed with the leadership team of the inpatient and outpatient BH settings. Since MBC may be a paradigm shift for some personnel on the BH team, the

discussion will include thoughts and opinions on the utility of MBC in contrast to previous practice. Examples of utility domains include effectiveness for tracking symptoms, observations of changes in patient engagement, and potential barriers for use (Oslin, Hoff, Mignogna & Resnick, 2019).

Act

Based on the evaluation and decisions made in the Study Phase, the current plan will be altered or refined with measures or procedures to improve effectiveness for subsequent PDSA cycles (Christoff, 2018; Crowfoot & Prasad, 2017). Any revisions in the protocol will be communicated to the leadership team and the nurses.

Future considerations for next PDSA cycles may include further changes in the protocol, measurement of adherence to the protocol, integration of the tool to the electronic health record (EHR), or other information technology (IT) platform and aggregation of data to inform subpopulation management.

Figure 1. Plan Do Study Act Cycle

Used with permission from the W. Edwards Deming Institute® (See Appendices A and B)

Model adapted for this project

- **Plan**

- Goal setting
- Current practice assessment
- Selection of standardized tool(s)
- Measurement-based care protocol
- Education and training development

- **Do**

- Knowledge and confidence pre-test
- Conduct education/training
- Knowledge and confidence post-test
- Knowledge and confidence post 2-month test
- Data implementation and collection PHQ-9 and protocol

- **Study**

- Data analysis of results
- Comparison with expected results
- Learnings
- Decision to adopt, adapt or abandon

- **Act**

- Considerations for next PDSA
 - Protocol adherence measurement
 - Protocol adjustments
 - Integration into EHR or IT platform
 - Aggregation of data

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A review of the available literature was conducted to answer the following questions: a) What is the epidemiologic background for major depression?; b) What are the criteria in evaluating tools for depression?; c) What is the evidence for MBC in depression?; and d) What are the benefits and barriers for MBC implementation? The literature search for this project was conducted using the following electronic databases: One Search, PubMed, CINAHL, and Google Scholar. The literature search included the following search terms: measurement-based care, outcome management, psychiatric measurement rating scales, clinical practice guidelines, behavioral health, mental health, depression, major depressive disorder, and depressive disorder. The search was limited to peer-reviewed articles about adults published in the English language from 2001-2019. Because a widely used tool to assess for depression was validated in 2001, the literature search started in that year.

Background of Major Depressive Disorder

Pathophysiology of Depression

The causes of depression are diverse and multifactorial and can include stressful life events, neurochemical imbalances, genetic susceptibility, medications, and various medical conditions, such as coronary heart disease and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (Harvard Health Publishing, 2017; Kasper et al., 2015).

A widely accepted chemical hypothesis that underlies potential causes of depression focuses on the role of neurotransmitters on mood regulation.

Neurotransmitters are chemical substances released by neurons, a major cell of the brain and peripheral nervous system, for the purpose of communicating with each other

(Littrell, 2015). Common neurotransmitters include serotonin, norepinephrine, and dopamine (Kasper et al., 2015; Littrell, 2015). The upstream neuron (presynaptic cell), communicates with the downstream neuron (postsynaptic cell) by releasing neurotransmitters into the gap or synapse between two (Littrell, 2015). Neurotransmitters may be taken in by receptors on the postsynaptic cell, which enables the transfer of the impulse. In this way, neurotransmitters serve as chemical messengers (Littrell, 2015).

Alternatively, the neurotransmitter may be taken back up, i.e., “re-uptake,” into the presynaptic cell, which lowers the amount of neurotransmitter in the synapse. By blocking this reuptake, the neurotransmitter levels in the synapse can be increased (Littrell, 2015). The most common class of antidepressant medications is that of selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs). Since deficiency or depletion in the levels of serotonin or other neurotransmitters is thought to be one of the causes of depression, the effectiveness of SSRIs in treating depression can be understood (Cowen & Browning, 2015; Kasper et al., 2015; Littrell, 2015).

Prevalence

The prevalence of major depression in adults in the United States ranges from 5-15% in the literature, with most large study estimates of 7-10% (Lépine & Briley, 2011; Pratt & Brody, 2014; Siu et al., 2016). There are varying prevalence rates of depression among the age groups, with the highest at 13% for ages 18-25, 8% for ages 26-45 and 5% for ages 50 and above (National Institute of Mental Health [NIMH], 2019). Among major ethnic groups, such as white, Hispanic, blacks, etc., major depressive prevalence ranges from 4-8%; however, it appears highest among adults who self-report two or more races at 11% (NIMH, 2019).

In the United States, females likely experience 1.5 to 3-fold higher rates of major depression than males, beginning in adolescence (APA, 2013). In a study of socioeconomic differences in depression rates, persons living below the federal poverty level experienced depression more than twice as frequently as persons living at or above the poverty level (Pratt & Brody, 2014). In a systematic review and meta-analysis of international data, lesbian, gay and bisexual people were at least twice the risk for depression compared to heterosexuals (King et al., 2008).

Comorbidities

The risk of depression is often higher in patients with serious medical illnesses such as heart disease and cancer (Krebber et al., 2014; May et al., 2017; Mental Health America [MHA], 2013). The incidence of comorbid depression is common in heart disease and increases the risk of death. For example, in a study of coronary artery disease, May et al. (2017) found a co-occurrence of 15% with a depression diagnosis, which was associated with a two-fold higher risk of death. In the specific example of myocardial infarction, the co-occurrence with depression is 40-65%, and the risk of death is 3-4 times within six months (May et al., 2017; MHA, 2013).

In a meta-analysis on the prevalence of depression in cancer patients, Krebber et al. (2014) reported a range of 8% to 24%, with variability depending on the type of instrument measuring depression, type of cancer, and treatment phase. Higher pooled prevalence was seen in bone and soft tissue, brain, and digestive tract cancer (Krebber et al., 2014). Another study found a high rate of depression in pancreatic cancer, which carries one of the worst prognoses among the different cancer types, with a prevalence of

14% to 76% (Mayr & Schmid, 2010). It is unknown whether depression is a promoter of tumor development or if pancreatic cancer is responsible for pathophysiological changes that lead to depression (Mayr & Schmid, 2010).

Research also shows the co-occurrence of depression with other BH conditions. For example, approximately one-third of adults with depression also exhibit substance misuse (MHA, 2013). Additionally, the most common underlying disorder for suicide or attempted suicide is major depression or bipolar disorder at 30-70% (MHA, 2013).

Economic Impact

The economic burden of mental conditions overall, and specifically depression, is high. The incremental economic burden of MDD was estimated at about \$80 million annually, including direct and indirect costs (Greenberg, Fournier, Sisitsky, Pike, & Kessler, 2015). More than half the costs were workplace-related, including absenteeism due to injury or illness (Greenberg et al., 2015).

Although mental health problems account for 27% of all disability costs, only 6.8% of healthcare spending is allocated to mental health treatments (Fortney et al., 2016; Melek, Norris & Paulus, 2014). The disparity between the underfunding of mental health services with that of other clinical services contributes to poor outcomes (Fortney et al., 2016). MBC may help to address chronic underfunding of mental health services by using objective measurements and aggregate data to quantify the value of mental health care interventions (Fortney et al., 2016).

Depression Diagnosis

Diagnostic Criteria

Major depressive disorder (MDD) is defined as a condition by the Diagnostic and Statistics Manual of Mental Disorder, 5th edition (DSM-V), as presenting with five or more of the following symptoms during the same two-week period, and which represent a change from previous function (APA, 2013):

- Depressed mood most of the day
- Diminished interest or pleasure in most all activities
- Significant weight loss or weight gain not due to dieting
- Insomnia or hypersomnia nearly every day
- Psychomotor agitation or retardation
- Fatigue or loss of energy
- Feelings of worthlessness
- Diminished ability to think or concentrate
- Recurrent thoughts of death

Screening Recommendations

Recommendations for the screening of depression from the U.S. Preventive Service Task Force (USPSTF) are for the general adult population, including pregnant and postpartum women (Siu et al., 2016). The USPSTF recommendation does not consider the cost in providing this service, and screening for depression should be implemented only if adequate systems are in place to support “accurate diagnosis, effective treatment, and appropriate follow-up” (Siu et al., 2016, p. 380). A systematic review of evidence on depression screening in primary care settings found depression

screening programs without staff-assisted support were unlikely to improve depression outcomes (O'Connor, Whitlock, Bell, & Gaynes, 2009). At a minimum, a designated nurse should notify a clinician of a positive screening result, followed by appropriate diagnosis and treatment with evidenced-based care or referral to a location that can provide necessary care (Siu et al., 2016).

Depression Assessment Tools

Patient-rated or self-report assessments are useful since patients are in the best position to report their own symptoms. However, clinicians may bring an objective perspective with experience and diagnostic knowledge (Glazer et al., 2018). An observational cohort study of 126 patients from ten academic sites found that combining patient and clinician-rated measures resulted in better prediction of at-risk suicidal ideation or behavior than either alone (Glazer et al., 2018). The tools used in this study were the Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9), the Clinical Global Impression Scale (CGI-S), and the Columbia-suicide Rating Scale (C-CSSRS) for detecting patient-rated suicide ideation (Glazer et al., 2018). The type and number of assessments used should be appropriate to the feasibility of specific practice settings.

Symptom rating scales are brief structured tools for patients to report their perceptions on the frequency and severity of symptoms (Oslin et al., 2019). Important attributes for selecting tools in practice include the following: a) psychometric validation for specific diagnoses; b) practicality of administration; c) ease of interpretation of results; d) sensitivity to changes in symptom frequency or severity over time; e) feasibility in a range of clinical settings; and f) acceptability to patients and clinicians (APA, 2013; Furukawa, 2010; The Kennedy Forum, 2015).

There are many depression assessment tools in the literature. The following are among the most cited:

Table 1

Comparison of Depression Tools

Name of Scale	Purpose	Number of Items	Self- or clinician-administered	Time (min)	Reliability	Validity
PHQ-9	Screen, Severity, Change	9	Self	3	++	++
BDI-II	Screen, Severity, Change	21	Self	5-10	+	++
QIDS	Severity, Change	16	Self, Clinician	5-10	+	++
HAM-D	Severity, Change	17	Clinician	15-30	+	++

PHQ-9=Patient Health Questionnaire; BDI = Beck Depression Inventory -2nd edition; QIDS = Quick Inventory of Depressive Symptomatology; HAM-D = Hamilton Rating Scale for Depression; +/++ = information in narrative

*Adapted from Furukawa, 2010

Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9). One of the most widely used tools for depression, PHQ-9, is used for screening, monitoring, and measuring severity (Furukawa, 2010). It consists of nine diagnostic criteria of the DSM-IV, such as depressed mood, change in appetite, and guilt or feeling of worthlessness (Furukawa, 2010; Kroenke, Spitzer, & Williams, 2001; Substance Abuse Mental Health Services Administration [SAMHSA], n.d.) The PHQ-9 is derived from PRIME-D, which is a diagnostic tool for common mental disorders (Kroenke et al., 2001). The PHQ-9 scores range from 0 to 27 (each item rates from 0 to 3 on a Likert scale) and is a well-validated patient rating assessment for depression (Glazer et al., 2018). The most consistently recommended cut point is ten or more, indicating more severe depressive symptoms and ≤ 4 for full remission (Furakawa, 2010; Glazer et al., 2018). In terms of feasibility, the PHQ-9 requires only a few minutes for the patient to fill out and less than one minute for

the clinician to score (Furukawa, 2010). The reliability is excellent with Cronbach's alpha of 0.89 (a measure of internal consistency) and test-retest reliability of 0.92 (Furukawa, 2010). Validity for screening was a sensitivity of 61-88% and specificity of 88-94% (Furukawa, 2010; Kroenke et al., 2001; Maurer, 2012). The original validation study of PHQ-9 was completed in 6,000 patients with a sensitivity of 88% and specificity of 88% for major depression (Kroenke et al., 2001). There are multiple versions of varying lengths of the PHQ such as PHQ-2, PHQ-4, and PHQ-9; the PHQ-2 has a sensitivity of 97% and specificity of 67% and is often used as an initial screening tool (Maurer, 2012). A recent meta-analysis of the PHQ-9 found a positive predictive value of 50% in primary care (Levis, Benedetti, & Thombs, 2019.)

The PHQ-9 tool with nine items is brief, but with good to excellent validity and reliability. For this reason, it was the selected tool for this project. It was administered more than once to monitor depressive symptoms. This tool is in public domain and downloadable from a Pfizer sponsored website which states that no permission is required to reproduce, translate, display or distribute the survey (Pfizer, 2020).

Beck Depression Inventory-II (BDI-II). The original version of BDI was published in 1961 with a revision in 1996 to align with DSM-IV criteria (Zimmerman, 2011) more closely. The 1996 2nd edition of the BDI is a 21-item self-report assessment widely used for measuring depression severity in adolescents and adults (Furukawa, 2010; Groth-Marnat & Wright, 2016). Each item is a series of four statements that describes symptom severity on an ordinal continuum from a score of 0 (mild) to severe (3) with a total score range of 0-63; in which 0-12 is minimal or no depression, 14-19 is mild depression, 20-28 is moderate, 29-63 is severe and ≤ 9 is remission (Furukawa,

2010; Von Glischinski, Von Brachel, & Hirschfeld, 2019). The estimated time to complete the survey is 5-10 minutes; internal consistency for reliability is good (Furukawa, 2010). The content validity with the 2nd version is improved with closer alignment with DSM-IV criteria (Furukawa, 2010; Groth-Marnot & Wright, 2016). The BDI-II is copyrighted, and users must pay a fee to purchase each copy administered (Zimmerman, 2011).

This tool was considered as an alternative to the PHQ-9. However, since it is longer (21 items), administering it repeatedly for MBC may make it less desirable than a briefer survey. Additionally, since this tool is copyrighted, it restricts the ease of use.

Quick Inventory of Depressive Symptomatology (QIDS). The QIDS is a 16-item assessment covering nine criteria symptoms of DSM-IV for MDD, that comes in self-report (QIDS-SR) or clinician-administered (QIDS-C) versions (Furukawa, 2010; Rush et al., 2006). The QIDS was designed to measure the overall severity of depressive symptoms (such as sleep, psychomotor, or appetite disturbances) and not intended as a diagnostic tool (Rush et al., 2006; Zimmerman, 2011). Each item is rated on the severity from 0-3 with a total score range of 27, with an estimated completion time of 5-10 minutes (Furukawa, 2010). Severity cut points are 11 for moderate depression, 16 for severe, 21 for very severe, and ≤ 5 for remission (Furukawa, 2010). Internal consistency and sensitivity to change are good, but limited test-retest reliability information is reported (Furukawa, 2010; Zimmerman, 2011). The QIDS is copyrighted by the authors, but available for unlimited use by clinicians (Zimmerman, 2011).

The QIDS tool has been widely used in depression research mainly to measure severity and change of symptoms but is not designed to use as a screening tool. For this

project, a tool with multiple purposes, such as screening, measuring change, and severity, was favored.

Hamilton Rating Scale for Depression (HAM-D or HRSD). The HAM-D is a 17-item clinician-rated assessment that was created almost 60 years ago to measure depression severity (Furukawa, 2010). Items are rated on a scale of 0-4 or 0-2 with a total range of 0-50, with remission ≤ 7 (Furukawa, 2010). Reliability is adequate, but there is a concern for validity as some items have not been updated to capture all of the DSM criteria (Furukawa, 2010). Additionally, the time for completion is the longest of the four assessments at 15-30 min.

Although the HAM-D has been used extensively, especially in clinical research, it was important for this project to have a patient-rated standardized tool. Additionally, this tool has not been updated to capture current DSM criteria and takes longer to administer than the other tools.

Measurement-Based Care

The use of MBC has shown improved outcomes for the individual patient, and benefits for clinicians, practices and healthcare organizations (The Kennedy Forum, 2015)

Benefits

Patients. Improved engagement, knowledge, satisfaction, and outcomes are potential benefits to patients who complete symptom rating scales (Fortney et al., 2016; The Kennedy Forum, 2015; Oslin et al., 2019). The process of filling out a measurement tool can help educate the patient about his or her diagnosis by increasing awareness and understanding of key symptoms (Steinfeld et al., 2016). Reviewing symptom rating

information with clinicians may help validate the way patients are feeling and mitigate self-blame, leading to opportunities for shared decision-making (Fortney et al., 2016; Kennedy Forum, 2015b).

Clinicians. Clinicians using standardized rating scales benefit from obtaining data to quantify progress. This is necessary, as demonstrated in a study looking at therapists' inability to detect deterioration in the outpatient setting. Hatfield, McCullough, Frantz, and Krieger (2010) found that therapists were able to detect a decline in only 21% of patients who worsened on a validated outcome questionnaire. In contrast, implementing MBC as a supplement to clinical judgment was associated with more frequent treatment adjustments, better patient engagement, and faster response to treatment (Fortney et al., 2016; Guo et al., 2015).

In a survey on the perception of MBC utility of 230 mental health clinicians (psychiatrists, nurses, psychologists, and social workers) from Veterans Administration (VA) medical centers, providers agreed that patient-rated outcomes were effective for tracking symptoms, monitoring progress and improving patient engagement (Oslin et al., 2019). Additionally, aggregated symptom severity data can be used to inform clinicians about the effectiveness of specific treatments, thereby impacting overall treatment algorithms or approaches (Guo et al., 2015; Oslin et al., 2019).

Healthcare Organizations. At the healthcare organization level, MBC allows practices to demonstrate the effectiveness of QI initiatives by providing aggregated quantitative treatment outcome data to payers and accreditation stakeholders (Fortney et al., 2016; Oslin et al., 2019). The field of BH is perceived as complex and lacking definitive outcome measures. This presents challenges for payers to provide appropriate

financial incentives such as pay-for-performance, for achieving specific quality metrics (Stewart, Lareef, Hadley, & Mandell, 2017). Specific examples of pay-for-performance measures in the behavioral setting are the following: patient length of stay, likelihood of having a psychiatric consultation, program completion, treatment initiation, treatment adherence, and treatment effectiveness (Pelonero & Johnson, 2007; Stewart et al., 2017; Unützer et al., 2012) By providing aggregated quantitative outcomes, MBC may allow the organization to improve quality scores such as pay-for-performance.

A major challenge in BH care delivery is the lack of integration of primary care and BH care services, which are often provided in silos (Unützer et al., 2012). MBC may serve to provide useful data to coordinate care between primary care and BH clinicians (Fortney et al., 2016).

Barriers

As mentioned above, the usage of MBC is low despite its benefits (Guo et al., 2015; Fortney et al., 2016; Lewis et al., 2019.). Oslin and colleagues (2019) reported high usage of rating scales but low usage documentation in the EHR. This could be due to the added time to document in the EHR or the criteria considered acceptable for EHR documentation (Oslin, 2019). Barriers for MBC usage include the following:

a) possibility that outcomes measures are inaccurate because patients are reluctant to give honest responses; b) provider concern with the burden of additional paperwork and time required for administration of assessment scales; c) provider concerns that patients may over or underestimate symptoms, and d) lack of provider knowledge about existing validated symptom rating scales (Fortney et al., 2016; The Kennedy Forum, 2015; Oslin et al., 2019; Steinfeld, 2016). Another potential barrier involves transitioning from paper

to EHR if necessary, which may require significant investment (The Kennedy Forum, 2015).

Depression Assessment Integration into EHR or IT Platform

Although depression assessment as MBC can be implemented successfully with paper and pen, four large-scale MBC programs: Veterans Affairs (VA), Department of Defense (DoD), Kaiser Permanente, and Washington State Federally Qualified Health Centers [FQHC]), integrated assessments into their EHR or another IT platform. All four programs targeted depression as a diagnosis and used PHQ-9 as an assessment tool.

The VA program developed an informatics software program called the BH Laboratory (BHL) for ongoing monitoring of patients during the acute phase of depression treatment. The program aids the user with the collection, scoring, interpretation, and accessibility of assessments by interfacing with the VA's EHR (Fortney et al., 2016).

Similarly, the FQHCs in Washington state use the Care Management Tracking System (CMTS), a web-based program that includes diagnostic specific self-scoring rating scales, e.g., PHQ-9, for care managers to collect and enter data (Fortney et al., 2016; Unützer et al., 2012). A symptom rating scale, e.g., PHQ-9, is used at treatment initiation and frequent follow-up sessions throughout the episode of care (Fortney et al., 2016; Unützer et al., 2012). CMTS detects when a patient is not responsive to treatment and sets up a flag for a psychiatric consultation review that provides recommendations to the primary care provider and care coordinator (Fortney et al., 2016). Using this framework, a quality improvement program with pay-for-performance incentives, found

a shorter time to treatment response in almost 8,000 patients with depression. (Fortney et al., 2016; Unützer et al., 2012).

In terms of data collection, all four programs used standardized scales, including PHQ-9, collected from patients either in person (e.g., waiting room), by phone, or on the patient portal (Fortney et al., 2016). To expedite data collection at the DoD specialty mental health centers, patients used handheld devices in the waiting room, which were immediately auto scored and presented in graphic form to the provider (Fortney et al., 2016). The data were integrated with the BH Data Portal (BHDP), a web-based system that reports outcomes that were routinely aggregated for quality improvement initiatives (Fortney et al., 2016).

Depression Treatment

Treatment for adults with MDD may be pharmacologic or nonpharmacologic (Qaseem, Barry, & Kansagara, 2016). Common nonpharmacologic psychological interventions include cognitive therapy, cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT), interpersonal therapy, and psychoanalysis (Qaseem et al., 2016; Rhoads & Murphy, 2014). In 2017, adults with MDD received the following treatment(s): 44% health professional and medication, 35% no treatment, 15% health professional only, and 6% medication only (NIMH, 2019).

Pharmacologic Treatment

Drugs that alter mood or behavior generally work as agonists (i.e., increases function) of specific neurotransmitters such as serotonin or dopamine (Littrell, 2015). The major classes of psychotropic drugs that treat depression include first-generation antidepressants, such as tricyclic anti-depressants and monoamine oxidase inhibitors, and

second-generation antidepressants (SGAs), such as SSRIs and selective serotonin norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors (Littrell, 2015; Qaseem et al., 2016). However, first-generation antidepressants are rarely used since SGAs have similar efficacy with lower toxicity in overdose (Qaseem et al., 2016). The reuptake inhibitors not only treat depression but are also indicated for other conditions, including anxiety and obsessive-compulsive disorder [OCD] (Littrell, 2015).

An important study combined the use of MBC and treatment protocols. The Sequenced Treatment Alternatives to Relieve Depression (STAR*D) study was the longest and most extensive study of MDD, involving over 4,000 patients, and was sponsored by the National Institute of Mental Health (Rush et al., 2004; Rush, 2011). Although the main objective was to study four different treatment levels of varying classes of anti-depressants, the study provided strong evidence of the value of measuring patient-reported outcomes. MBC enhanced safe titration by using the HAM-D, QIDS, and other tools, in combination with a treatment algorithm (Rush, 2011). Clinicians reported feeling more comfortable in dose escalations when using metrics linked to a medication algorithm, as the doses used in the trial were generally higher than those reported from practice surveys (Rush, 2011). Using a similar protocol to STAR*D, Guo et al. (2015) noted similar benefits from the use of MBC versus standard treatment.

Non-pharmacologic Treatment

Cognitive Behavioral Therapy. Cognitive behavioral therapy targets a patient's thinking process to correct false self-beliefs and faulty assumptions so that alternative perspectives can be considered (Qaseem et al., 2016; Rhoads & Murphy, 2014). CBT focuses on the thoughts and behavior that form problematic emotional reactions and

consequences that result in dysfunctional attitudes and behaviors. The focus of therapy is to examine cognitive errors and learned patterns of thinking to transition to new, objective, evidenced-based thought patterns, and behavioral skills (Rhoads & Murphy, 2014). CBT is usually short-term (6 to 18 sessions), structured and commonly used in depression, anxiety disorders, addictions and personality disorders (Rhoads & Murphy, 2014). In a systematic review of the literature and the American College of Physicians' clinical practice guideline, the recommendation was made for clinicians to select between CBT or SGAs for treatment of major depressive disorder (Qaseem et al., 2016). Also, moderate evidence showed CBT and SGAs were similarly effective (Littrell, 2015; Qaseem et al., 2016).

Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation. Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (TMS), also known as repetitive TMS (rTMS), is a technique that uses an external varying magnetic field to induce an electric current in the brain to the region involved in mood regulation and depression (Gaynes et al., 2014; Littrell, 2015). TMS was approved by the US Food and Drug Administration in 2008 for treatment of MDD who failed to achieve satisfactory improvement from previous antidepressant medication (Gaynes et al., 2014). Meta-analyses suggest similar response and remission rates to those of antidepressants (Gaynes et al., 2014; The Medical Letter, 2019; Serafini et al., 2015).

Electroconvulsive therapy. Electroconvulsive therapy (ECT) is a procedure done under general anesthesia in which electric currents are passed through the brain, triggering a brief seizure (Sackheim, 2017). It appears ECT causes changes in brain chemistry that results in improvement of symptoms (Sackheim, 2017). ECT is an effective treatment for MDD with or without psychotic features, especially for reducing

suicidal ideation (Kellner, Li, Farber, Geduldig & Ahle, 2016; Rhodes & Murphy, 2014). Cognitive adverse effects have limited its acceptance, especially retrograde amnesia, but more modern ECT appears to be better tolerated (Sackeim, 2017). Significant progress in refining the ECT stimulus and more precise titration to individual seizure thresholds in recent years makes ECT an effective and underused intervention (The Medical Letter, 2019; Sackheim 2017).

Exercise. The role of exercise as a treatment for depression has been controversial. While several studies have suggested exercise is a beneficial intervention for depression, the magnitude of effectiveness among published studies is variable (Qaseem et al., 2016). However, a recent meta-analysis concludes that publication bias resulted in an underestimation of the benefit of exercise. The paper concluded that exercise is an evidence-based treatment for depression (Schuch et al., 2016).

Summary of Literature

Based on the overall prevalence of MDD in the adult US population, the high comorbidity rates with common medical and behavioral health conditions, and the importance of this behavioral health diagnosis nationwide (and to this project facility), there is a need to ensure early screening and optimal management of MDD patients. The United States Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF) recommends screening all adults on if adequate systems are in place for accurate diagnosis, treatment, and follow-up (Siu et al., 2016). To this end, developing and implementing a protocol to utilize a standardized tool to screen and monitor the progress of MDD patients in a behavioral health setting is needed.

There are many well-researched assessments for depression available for use. The PHQ-9 is one of the shortest to complete at 3 minutes, with good to excellent validity and reliability, available in the public domain, and quick to score. For these reasons, the PHQ-9 was selected as the optimal choice for this project. The focus of this project was to monitor the progress and outcomes of MDD patients who were previously screened and diagnosed.

Despite the proven benefits of MBC in the BH settings as evidenced-based practice, less than 20% of clinicians have adopted its use (Lewis et al., 2015). Additionally, there is limited information about using MBC in different practice settings, particularly for the inpatient hospital setting.

METHODS

As stated above, the purpose of this QI project was to develop, implement, and evaluate a protocol for utilization of the PHQ-9 for patients in BH settings. The goal was to assure compliance with TJC revised BH Care Outcome Measures Standard (TJC, 2017). The project included creating the protocol for measuring PHQ-9 utilization, as well as evaluating BH personnel on their knowledge and confidence in implementing the protocol. The following clinical practice questions were addressed:

1. What is the baseline knowledge of BHS staff regarding the revised CTS standard, MBC, depression assessment using PHQ-9, and the new protocol?
2. What is the impact of education and training on staff knowledge and confidence in using the revised CTS standard, MBC, PHQ-9, and protocol?
3. What is the adherence by the BHS staff to the protocol as measured by the total PHQ-9 assessments for the MDD population in a given month?

4. What is the aggregate patient response of CTS? This is measured by the change in PHQ-9 scores from admission to discharge monthly as presented by:
- a) Mean aggregate change in scores
 - b) Change in scores grouped in quartiles

Setting and Sample

The settings for the project were the inpatient and outpatient BH departments at a medium-sized, multi-specialty hospital in southern California. The services that are offered for the inpatient setting are for all psychiatric diagnoses, including substance misuse, depression, and psychosis. The average length of stay for inpatients is 3-5 days. Those provided for the outpatient setting include services for bipolar disorder, major depressive disorder, and postpartum depression. The average episode of care for outpatients is 4-6 weeks. For this study, only MDD patients were targeted for the protocol.

A convenience sample of 44 BH personnel working in the inpatient and outpatient BHS was included for the pre- and post-test assessments of knowledge and confidence in using the MDD MBC protocol. While in-service educational attendance was mandatory as directed by leadership, the in-service evaluation (pre and post-tests) was voluntary. The BH personnel targeted for in-services consisted of registered nurses (RNs), nurse practitioners, therapists, social workers, and unit secretaries. The education program was presented in eight in-services to accommodate different shifts. Additionally, a written presentation was available for BH personnel who were unable to attend in person and as reinforcement for content covered at the education session.

Ethical Considerations

Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval was requested and granted as exempt status from both the project hospital and California State University, Los Angeles. There was a low risk to the participants. Since in-service education surveys were voluntary, the patient PHQ-9 score data were de-identified, and the records maintained in a secure location. Written, informed consent was requested from the participants taking the pre- and post-test surveys.

Project Design

The study design was a quality improvement project to implement the new protocol for MDD patients to assure compliance with regulatory requirements for safe, effective, and measurable care. The leadership team consisted of the BHS hospital director, and both inpatient and outpatient BHS managers. These stakeholders were consulted throughout the project for their opinions and recommendations to ensure fit, feasibility, and preferences.

Instruments

1. Inservice Surveys

The pre- and post-education tests were administered on Survey Monkey by hard copy, email, or cellphone link (See Appendix C). If administered by hard copy, the data were manually inputted to the Survey Monkey password-protected website. No identifying data were sought from Survey Monkey. Educational domains were role classification, measurement-based care, the revised Joint Commission CTS standard, and the confidence scale. The five confidence statements were adapted from the Confidence Scale (C-scale) (permission obtained from Wolters Kluwer, see Appendix D), which

evaluates perceived confidence to perform a task (Grundy, 1993). This validated tool uses a Likert-like scale ranging from “Not at all” to “Absolutely all of it.” The C-scale’s test-retest correlation coefficient using Spearman’s rank-order was .89 (Grundy, 1993). The correlation coefficient with two other confidence scales ranged from .58-.80 and .64-.77 and internal consistency using Cronbach’s alpha ranged from .84-.93 (Grundy, 1993).

2. Patient Health Questionnaire-9

The PHQ-9 is a nine-question self-report survey that was the key focus of the protocol as a monitoring tool to assess the progress and outcomes of MDD patients (See Appendix E). The questionnaire uses a Likert-type scale for the patient to rate how often they have been bothered by specific problems within the previous two weeks. The patient rates each question on a scale ranging from 0 to 3 from “not at all” (0) to “nearly every day” (3). Total scores range from 0-27. As previously mentioned, the reliability is excellent with Cronbach’s alpha of .89, test-retest reliability of .92, sensitivity of 88%, and specificity of 88% for major depression (Furukawa, 2010, Kroenke et al., 2001).). This survey is in the public domain and does not require permission to use.

3. Measurement-Based Care of Depression Protocol (MBC Depression Protocol)

The PHQ-9 was targeted to all patients diagnosed with MDD who were admitted to the outpatient and inpatient BH settings at the hospital (See Appendix F). The MBC Depression Protocol recommends a frequency of administering the PHQ-9 at least three times during the episode of care. The MBC Depression Protocol recommends lower

intensity interventions for minimal to mild depression versus more intensive interventions for more severe depression. For example, if the PHQ-9 score is less than 15, fewer intensive interventions are recommended, such as watchful waiting. If the score is 15 or higher, a holistic approach is recommended that includes implementation of evidence-based pharmacological and non-pharmacological (mind, body, and spirit) interventions.

4. Depression Data Collection Tool

The depression data collection tool (Excel spreadsheet) was designed for recording of de-identified PHQ-9 scores. Formulas are embedded in the Excel spreadsheet; they automatically calculate the change in scores and graph aggregate scores in quartiles. (See Appendix G). Additionally, embedded formulas calculate protocol adherence measures, such as the number of PHQ-9 surveys given for the MDD population. The data collection tool also allows the recording of other data such as the number of MDD medications, procedures (ECT or TMS), and assigned clinicians. Due to time constraints, the latter data were not collected and will be listed as one of the future recommendations.

Data Collection and Interventions

An education program was developed regarding the MBC Depression Protocol. Verbal reminders from the inpatient and outpatient managers for the in-services and pre-/post-tests were made. Assessment for knowledge and confidence in using the selected tool and protocol was created and administered at baseline (pre-education) and immediately post-education. The education program was delivered as in-service training using PowerPoint or hard copy. Data from the pre- and post-tests were analyzed using

SPSS Statistics version 26. Evaluation of the data collection points was completed and shared with the leadership team.

Outpatient BHS:

PHQ-9 surveys were recommended on admission to the program and every two weeks up to and including the end of the program. BH staff administered and scored PHQ-9 surveys, recorded treatment goals, and plans in the EHR and filed the completed PHQ-9 surveys in the manager's office. The outpatient manager and project author recorded the survey scores in the data collection tool, which enabled analysis of the MDD population on a monthly basis.

Inpatient BHS

The PHQ-9 administration for the inpatient setting will occur on admission, day 3, and upon discharge. Nurses and other designated personnel will administer and score PHQ-9 surveys, record treatment plans in the EHR, and file the completed PHQ-9 surveys in the appointed notebook at the nurses' station. Due to time limitations, the implementation of the protocol in the inpatient setting was not performed but is a future plan to complete.

RESULTS

Findings

In-service Education

Total attendance for in-services was 49 of 57 (86%) BHS personnel (12 outpatient staff and 37 inpatient staff). Survey response rates were the following: Pre-tests 38 of 57 (64%), post-test 44 of 57 (77%). The roles of survey respondents were as follows from the post-test data:

Table 2

Roles of Behavioral Health Setting Personnel Respondents

Role	Number	Percentage
Registered Nurse	24	55%
Nurse Practitioner	2	4%
Social Worker	10	23%
Therapist	3	7%
Other	5	11%
Total Respondents	44	

In-services learning outcomes were as follows: 1) Identification of the rationale and benefits of MBC; 2) Description of the revisions for the Behavioral Health Care Outcomes Measures Standard (CTS 03.01.09); 3) Identification of three key uses of the PHQ-9 for depression assessment, and 4) Identification of the recommended frequency for PHQ-9 administration in the MBC Depression Protocol.

The domains of the pre and post-test were the following: 1) Measurement-based Care and Joint Commission measure (2 questions); 2) PHQ-9 (4 questions); and 3)

MDD MBC Protocol (4 questions). The goal of the in-services was to achieve a 10% improvement in scores from pre-test to post-test. Results were as follows: Pre-test scores (n=38) 59% (mean), 19% (SD); and Post-test score (n=44) 78% (mean), 15% (SD). The improvement was 32% ($p=0.045$). Data from the pre- and post-tests were analyzed using SPSS Statistics version 26. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics.

Categorical variables were expressed as numbers and percentages. Continuous variables were expressed as mean since the data is normally distributed. Means were compared using independent T-tests since the pre and post data were not paired to assure the same participants. Statistical significance was set at an alpha of 0.05.

The mean pre-test score for the outpatient staff on the pre-test was 70% (vs. 56% for the inpatient staff). In terms of difficulty ranking of test questions, the domain most challenging was regarding the new protocol. The difficulty ranking of questions results have been displayed for both pre-test and post-test (Table 3).

Table 3

Difficulty Ranking of Questions

Pre-test Questions (10)	Difficulty	Average Score
Q8 The number of PHQ-9 surveys administered should optimally be at least:	1	38%
Q11 If the patient scores 15 on the PHQ-9 the following actions should be taken EXCEPT:	2	33%
Q6 The PHQ-9 score of ___ has a sensitivity of 88% and a specificity of 88% for major depression in the original validation paper (Kroenke, Spitzer & Williams, 2001)?	3	38%
Q9 If the initial score of the PHQ-9 is less than 9, the following actions should be taken EXCEPT:	4	42%
Q4 Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9) asks patients to rate their symptoms over what time period?	5	66%
Q10 If question 9 on suicide ideation (>0) is positive, the following action should be taken:	6	68%
Q2 The revised Care, Treatment, and Services (CTS) Standard (Behavioral Health Care Outcomes Measure Standard) of the Joint Commission requires all of the follow EXCEPT:	6	68%
Q7 The PHQ-9 is to be administered	8	76%
Q3 Measurement-based Care (MBC) is defined as the practice of basing clinical care	9	86%

Q5 The purpose(s) of the PHQ-9 is to:	10	92%
<hr/>		
Post-test Questions	Difficulty	Average Score
<hr/>		
Q9 If the initial score of the PHQ-9 is less than 9, the following actions should be taken EXCEPT:	1	41%
Q11 If the patient scores 15 on the PHQ-9 the following actions should be taken EXCEPT:	2	67%
Q8 The number of PHQ-9 surveys administered should optimally be at least:	3	69%
Q6 The PHQ-9 score of ___ has a sensitivity of 88% and a specificity of 88% for major depression in the original validation paper (Kroenke, Spitzer & Williams, 2001)?	4	70%
Q10 If question 9 on suicide ideation (>0) is positive, the following action should be taken:	5	73%
Q4 Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9) asks patients to rate their symptoms over what time period?	6	91%
Q2 The revised Care, Treatment, and Services (CTS) Standard (Behavioral Health Care Outcomes Measure Standard) of the Joint Commission requires all of the follow EXCEPT:	7	91%
Q3 Measurement-based Care (MBC) is defined as the practice of basing clinical care	8	95%
Q7 The PHQ-9 is to be administered	9	98%

Q5 The purpose(s) of the PHQ-9 is to: 10 98%

The results of the five questions on confidence (rated from zero to five) were as follows: Weighted average ranges were pre-test (2.46-2.89) to post-test (4.16-4.43), showing significant improvement ($p < 0.001$) (See Table 4). The questions asked the respondent to select from a five-point scale (from 1 to 5) on each statement from “Not at all” to “Absolutely all of it” to best describe the learner’s perception of their ability to administer the PHQ-9 and implement the MBC depression protocol for questions 12 - 16 (See Appendix C).

Table 4

Confidence Score Responses

Protocol Adherence

Protocol adherence was measured by the total number of PHQ-9 surveys administered per MDD patient monthly. In the outpatient BHS for December 2019 and January 2020, protocol adherence was three PHQ-9s per patient, which is 100% or the

targeted amount. The month and number of outpatient MDD patient PHQ-9s were as follows: December 2019 (10) and January 2020 (10) for a total of twenty scores.

Inpatient BHS PHQ-9 implementation was just starting at the time of this writing, so data are not yet available. For depression severity rating, MDD patients who had an initial PHQ-9 of 10 or higher (signifying moderate to severe depression) in the outpatient BHS were as follows: December 2019 (10/10 or 100%) and January 2020 (10/10 or 100%).

Aggregate Patient Response

For the outpatient BHS, the graph below illustrates the percentage of MDD patients by the change in PHQ-9 scores within quartile ranges (See Table 5). For example, 30% of patients experienced a PHQ-9 score change in the range of 51-75% from the initial PHQ-9 to the end of the episode of care. The mean aggregate

Table 5

Aggregate PHQ-9 Score Change in MDD Outpatients

Combined December 2019 and January 2020 (n=20)

% of MDD Patients by PHQ-9 Score Change

improvement in PHQ-9 scores in the outpatient BHS were the following: December 2019 (61%, n=10) and January 2020 (51%, n=10). The combined mean change for two months was 56%.

Evaluation and Outcomes

This QI project follows a Plan, Do, Study, Act (PDSA) framework. The “plan” stage included reviewing the literature for tools appropriate to monitor MDD patients, the development of a new MBC depression protocol, and the development of in-service education and evaluation for staff. The PHQ-9 was selected as a monitoring tool for MDD patients following the literature review. The PHQ-9 was already an approved survey at the hospital site and available in their EHR, although it was previously used more frequently by outpatient than by inpatient staff. The development of the MBC depression protocol by the leadership team and project author was adapted based on the original interpretation of PHQ-9 (Kroenke & Spitzer, 2002), the mission and values of the project hospital, and evidence-based interventions. Additionally, a data collection tool was created by the leadership team and project author to capture the PHQ-9 scores and embed functions such as calculation of metrics and graphing. The in-service program was created to educate personnel on the recently revised JC standard based on MBC principles and the MBC depression protocol, which included PHQ-9 administration.

The implementation (“do” stage) of in-service education occurred in ten sessions with groups of two to ten people. The leadership team preferred small groups for the in-service session to enable optimal learning and opportunity for discussion as needed. The outpatient BHS staff was composed of twelve therapists, nurse practitioners (NPs), nurses, and social workers, who already were using PHQ-9 surveys as a regular part of

their therapy sessions. It had been common practice within the department to administer and collect the PHQ-9 surveys to patients at the start of group sessions, often occurring weekly. Because the outpatient staff was more familiar with the PHQ-9, the focus for their in-service sessions prioritized the newly revised CTS Joint Commission measure (TJC, 2017) and protocol rather than on the PHQ-9. In contrast, the inpatient in-services were focused on PHQ-9 training first, then on the other domains.

In the “study” stage, three sets of metrics were analyzed: in-service education, protocol adherence, and patient response (PHQ-9 score changes). In contrast to the inpatient pre-test scores, the higher outpatient pre-test scores were probably due to their familiarity with PHQ-9. Overall the most challenging questions were related to the MBC Depression Protocol, which was new to both the inpatient and outpatient staff. The pre-test scores improved by about a third, indicating a significant effect of the in-service training. The 20% improvement in knowledge scores following the in-service sessions met the learning outcome goal. Confidence scores also improved significantly in almost doubling the weighted average ranges from pre-test (2.4-2.8) to post-Test (4.16-4.4).

The target of protocol adherence was met in the outpatient setting. However, as previously noted, the inpatient protocol implementation had not yet started, so data were not available.

During the episodes of care for this project, there was a significant improvement (56% on average) in PHQ-9 scores. Coley et al. (2019) define response to treatment as a 50% change in initial PHQ-9 scores. Kroenke, Spitzer, and Williams (2001) suggest that a preliminary approach to interpreting a clinical response in depression is a PHQ-9 score less than ten and a 50% decline from pretreatment scores.

The “act” stage, based on the above evaluation, identifies how subsequent PDSAs will be adopted, adapted, or abandoned. Based on the findings to date, this project was adopted. Due to time limitations and incomplete implementation in the inpatient setting, PHQ-9 administration and protocol implementation will continue. Additionally, PHQ-9 administration will be considered in other diagnoses, such as bipolar disorders. Other recommendations included automating PHQ-9 administration and downloading scores into an electronic platform integrated into the EHR, training other relevant BH personnel such as LVNs, and consideration of collecting and analyzing other tools relevant to the most prevalent diagnostic BH conditions.

DISCUSSION

The goal of this QI project was to assure compliance with TJC revised BH Care Outcome Measures Standard (TJC, 2017). The recently revised standard was based on MBC research in BH, which demonstrated improved treatment outcomes and greater patient engagement (Guo et al., 2015; Steinfeld et al., 2016). However, fewer than 20% of BH clinicians have adopted MBC (Lewis et al., 2019; Scott & Lewis, 2015). The hospital site was looking to improve its current MBC process especially in extracting outcomes information to support compliance with regulatory requirements for safe, effective, and measurable care.

Key Findings

In addressing the four clinical practice questions previously identified, the findings were as follows: 1) The mean pre-test knowledge of the BHS staff covering the four domains of MBC, TJC measure, PHQ-9, and the MBC Depression Protocol was 59% and the mean confidence score was 2.7 (of 5); 2) the post-test education knowledge

score was 78%, representing a significant improvement of 32% ($p = 0.045$) and the post mean confidence score was 4.3 ($p < 0.001$); 3) adherence by the outpatient staff to the protocol of three PHQ-9 surveys per patient was met at 100%; and 4) the mean monthly aggregate score change for MDD patients was 56%. The changes in PHQ-9 scores when grouped in quartiles were as follows: Worsening results (10%); improving results: 0-25% (10%), 26-50% (15%), 51-75% (30%), and 76-100% (35%).

Due to time restrictions, the inpatient setting data was not available. Since PHQ-9 administration is new to the inpatient setting, expectation of protocol adherence would likely be gradual with the goal to adopt consistency within 3-6 months post-implementation.

Although MBC has been well researched in terms of benefits to patients, clinicians, and organizations over the past two decades, there has been a lag time in the application of evidence-based research to practice. TJC measure is an effective way of motivating organizations to adopt evidenced-based research by setting standards such as CTS 03.01.09 that require the use of MBC for accreditation. Educating BH staff and setting a protocol to put MBC into practice is the first step in supporting compliance with this measure. Furthermore, incorporating MBC in BH curriculum for clinicians is important to propagate its adoption in practice.

This project was supported by the leadership of the project site not only to support compliance measure but to identify opportunities to improve patient outcomes. This was accomplished by utilizing PHQ-9 scores to enhance and adjust treatment interventions. Although a numerical goal for aggregate patient response was not pre-specified, a depression metric for Health Effectiveness Data Information Set (HEDIS) by the National

Committee for Quality Assurance (NCQA) is a treatment response of 50% or greater from the initial PHQ-9 score (Coley et al., 2019). A collective, aggregate score of 56% for the MDD is indicative of the overall response of the CTS provided by the project site.

Limitations

The limitations of the project included the following: 1) A short duration of study resulted in incomplete inpatient implementation. The greater number of staff on the inpatient side and less familiarity with the PHQ-9 required a longer education period for the small group in-services and ramp-up period to start the administration of PHQ-9s; 2) since the QI project was implemented in the outpatient BH setting only, there was a small sample size for the de-identified PHQ-9 scores; 3) the data collection tool originally was designed to include the collection of other information for future analysis such as the number of depression medications, treatment procedures and assigned clinician. This was not completed due to time restrictions, and 4) PHQ-9 collection and data input was manual, which is more time-consuming. The project site was in transition from one EHR to another, so a separate data collection tool was created. However, the tool was enhanced with embedded formulas and auto-generated graphs to enable aggregate analysis.

Future recommendations include the following: Continuation of inpatient BH setting implementation; expansion of PHQ-9 administration to other BH diagnoses such as bipolar disorders; education of all members of the BH team; automation and integration of PHQ-9 collection to a decision support platform with integration into the new EHR; collection of other variables such as medications, procedures and assigned clinicians for future analysis; and expansion of MBC to other relevant standardized tools.

Conclusion

A protocol to monitor and treat MDD patients was successfully set up and adhered to in the outpatient BH setting. Analysis of the PHQ-9 scores for the outpatient MDD population indicated substantial treatment response. However, due to time limitations, implementation for the inpatient BH setting was not completed. The data collection tool with embedded calculations and graphing function facilitated data analysis and reporting to support the JC measure.

The principal DNP Essentials supported by this project are Essential II: Organizational and Systems Leadership for Quality Improvement and Systems Thinking, Essential VI: Interprofessional Collaboration for Improving Patient and Population Health, and Essential VII: Clinical Prevention and Population Health for Improving the Nation's Health (American Association of Colleges of Nursing, 2006).

Though evidence-based, MBC has not been widely adopted in behavioral health. PHQ-9 as a monitoring tool may function as a “lab” test for depression by providing data points that quantify progress to guide and adjust treatment plans over time. Patient-reported outcomes data enables enhanced patient awareness, engagement and self-management, improved organizational coordination of care and demonstrates the effectiveness of QI initiatives.

In conclusion, this DNP project significantly supported the organization's goal of implementing and evaluating MBC with PHQ-9 for the MDD patients in the outpatient BHS. This is in compliance with TJC CTS 03.01.09 (Behavioral Health Care Outcomes Measure Standard). Whether the methods in this project could have a similar effect in the inpatient BHS is uncertain. MBC will lead to improved patient-centric care *in the*

outpatient BHS by quantifying the progress and outcomes of care, treatment, and services provided. Quantifying behavioral health conditions such as depression is long overdue and necessary in order to successfully integrate behavioral health into primary care settings.

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APPENDIX A

PERMISSION TO USE PDSA IMAGE

3/20/2019

Cal State Fullerton Mail - Inquiry reply – use of PDSA model

Janice Lew <lewjanic@csu.fullerton.edu>

Inquiry reply – use of PDSA model

Bill Bellows <bill@deming.org>
 To: lewjanic@csu.fullerton.edu

Tue, Mar 19, 2019 at 5:52 PM

Janice - good evening...

Thank you for reaching out to us at The W. Edwards Deming Institute®.

Your request is copied below:

Comments: Requesting permission to use the PDSA cycle image and concepts in my Doctor of Nursing Practice project. My project is on measurement-based care in behavioral health. Are there various images you would prefer for me to use? Thank you, Janice Lew

Relative to your reference to the Plan-Do-Study-Act cycle, we appreciate your interest in reproducing Dr. Deming's remarkable "PDSA" model in your project.

While The Deming Institute owns the copyright to Dr. Deming's book, *The New Economics*, in which the PDSA model appears, the reprint rights to this book are owned by our publisher, MIT Press. As such, I will follow this note with an email to Pamela Quick, our MIT Press contact, whose permission is needed for your plans to reference the PDSA model.

In addition, we gladly grant you permission to use the PDSA graphic on our website, <https://deming.org/explore/p-d-s-a>. In association with your use, please include this "permission" text; "PDSA Model courtesy of The W. Edwards Deming Institute®."

Let me know if you have any questions on these permissions.

Best regards...

Bill

Bill Bellows, Ph.D.
 Deputy Director
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bill@deming.org
<https://deming.org/deming-institute/our-team/bill-bellows%2c-phd>
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APPENDIX B
PERMISSION TO USE PDSA

Inquiry reply – permission to use the PDSA Model from *The New Economics*

Pamela L Quick [REDACTED]
To: Bill Bellows [REDACTED]
Cc: "lewjanic@csu.fullerton.edu" <lewjanic@csu.fullerton.edu>

Mon, Mar 25, 2019 at 10:54 AM

Dear Bill,

Thank you for forwarding this request.

Janice, I am happy to grant nonexclusive permission to reprint the PDSA Model from *The New Economics* in your forthcoming doctoral project, for academic noncommercial purposes. Please indicate that the figure is reprinted courtesy of The MIT Press from *The New Economics for Industry, Government, Education, second edition*, by W. Edwards Deming.

Please let me know if you have further questions,

Pamela

Pamela Quick
Subsidiary Rights Manager
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[Quoted text hidden]

APPENDIX C

IN-SERVICE EVALUATION

Depression Measurement-based Care Pre-/Post-Test 2020 CSULA

Title of Project: Depression Assessment as Measurement-based Care

To Project Participant:

You are invited to take part in a research project conducted by Dr. Glenn Raup (Co-Investigator and preceptor), Dr. Darlene Finocchiaro (PI), Associated Professor of Nursing, and Janice Lew (Co-Investigator), a graduate student at California State University, Los Angeles. In this project we hope to learn more about depression assessment as measurement-based care. You were selected to participate in this study because you are a healthcare provider in the behavior health setting at St. Joseph Hospital and are 18 years or older. We hope that our research will lead to learning about the benefits of implementing a protocol for using depression assessment (Patient Health Questionnaire-9 [PHQ-9]) to quantify the progress of patients with depression.

You will be educated to implement a protocol for patients with depression through an in-service. This will include taking one pre-test and two post-tests (immediately and one month post in-service) via Survey Monkey. Expected time to complete the Survey Monkey pre-/post-tests is 10 minutes for each survey. After the in-service, protocol implementation will include PHQ-9 administration per protocol; scoring and documentation of questionnaires for patients with depression in the usual manner in the electronic medical record (EMR); documentation of action plans, medications and procedures in the usual manner in the EMR (approximately 5 minutes for administration of PHQ-9 survey per patient and 5 minutes scoring and documentation of survey score in EMR = 10 minutes total estimated time per patient surveyed). Protocol monitoring will be ongoing as this is necessary to meet Joint Commission Regulation.

There are minimal risks to this study: Surveys are not collecting identifying information; participants may choose to not answer any questions they are not comfortable answering and may leave the survey at any time without finishing. If you choose not to participate in the study, there is no penalty or loss of benefits to which you are entitled.

Reports resulting from this study will not identify you as a participant. Your survey answers will be sent to a link at SurveyMonkey.com where data will be stored in a password protected electronic format. Survey Monkey does not collect identifying information such as your name, email address, or IP address. Therefore, your responses will remain anonymous and survey participation is voluntary. Protocol implementation and analysis will be reported with aggregate, de-identified PHQ-9 scores.

If you have any questions about this research at any time, please call the Co-Investigator/Preceptor, Dr. Glenn Raup at 714-771-8257 or email at glenn.raup@stjoe.org, PI, Dr. Darlene Finocchiaro at 323-343-5663 or email dfinocc@exchange.calstatela.edu, or Co-Investigator, Janice Lew at 626-277-1737 or email lewjanic@csu.fullerton.edu.

THIS PROJECT HAS BEEN DETERMINED TO BE EXEMPT FROM REVIEW AND APPROVAL BY THE CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LOS ANGELES INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD FOR THE PROTECTION OF HUMAN SUBJECTS IN RESEARCH

Please choose the BEST answer for each question:

1. What is your primary role in BHS? (select one)

- RN
- LVN/LPN
- Nurse Practitioner
- Social Worker
- Therapist
- Other (please specify)

2. The revised Care, Treatment, and Services (CTS) Standard (Behavioral Health Care Outcomes Measure Standard) of the Joint Commission requires all of the following **EXCEPT**:

- Use of a standardized tool to monitor individual progress
- Use of the results of the tool to inform the goals and treatment plan of the individual
- Use of data for clinical trials
- Use of aggregate data to evaluate outcomes of care, treatment and services provided to the population(s) served

3. Measurement-Based Care (MBC) is defined as the practice of basing clinical care

- on a one-time comprehensive assessment and evaluation of a patient's mental state
- on a structured clinical interview for DSM-V (SCID-5)
- on patient data collected throughout treatment using reliable and valid tools
- on the most recent clinical guideline

4. Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9) asks patients to rate their symptoms from what time period?

- Over the last 48 hours
- Over the last 2 weeks
- Over the last month
- Over the last year

5. The purpose(s) of the PHQ-9 is to:

- Screen for depression
- Measure severity of depression
- Measure change in depression
- All of the above

6. The PHQ-9 score of _____ has a sensitivity of 88% and a specificity of 88% for major depression in the original validation paper (Kroenke, Spitzer & Williams, 2001)?

- ≥ 5
- ≥ 10
- ≥ 15
- ≥ 20

Questions 7 to 11 pertain to the protocol for Measurement-Based Care (MBC) for Major Depressive Disorder (MDD) to be used at this hospital (inpatient and outpatient BHS):

7. The PHQ-9 is to be administered:

- Only if ordered by a psychiatrist
- Only if ordered by a physician
- Only to patients with a positive Columbia Suicide Screening Rating Scale (CSSR) score
- By the nurse or therapist to every patient admitted with MDD

8. The number of PHQ-9 surveys administered (either inpatient or outpatient) should **optimally** be at least:

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

9. If the initial score of the PHQ-9 is less than 9, the following actions should be taken **EXCEPT**:

- Documentation of a watchful waiting action plan
- Documentation of the PHQ-9 score with no further action required
- Provision of appropriate resources to the patient
- Consider implementation of medical management if not already in progress

10. If question 9 on suicidal ideation is positive (>0) the following action should be taken:

- Re-administer the PHQ-9 in one week
- Consider administering (or re-administering) the suicide assessment (Columbia Suicide Severity Rating Scale [C-SSRS]) as suicidal ideation noted during a depression assessment should trigger further action
- Call the Psychiatric Emergency Team
- Document an action plan for exercise

11. If the patient scores 15 on the PHQ-9 the following actions should be taken **EXCEPT**:

- Document a watchful waiting action plan
- Implement evidence-based practice (EBP) actions for pharmacological/procedural management of depression
- Implement EBP for non-pharmacological management of depression for mind care, body care and spirit care
- Ensure/coordinate further evaluation by a qualified mental health clinician and document discussions with provider about interventions related to depression and impact on depression behaviors

For the following (remaining) questions, select the number which **BEST** describes how you perceive your current ability to administer the PHQ-9 and implement the protocol for Measurement-based care (MBC) for Major Depressive Disorder (MDD) to be used at this hospital (BHS):

12. My knowledge is sufficient

Not at all certain	Certain for only a few steps	Fairly certain for a good number of steps	Certain for almost all steps	Absolutely certain for all steps
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

13. I feel that I can perform the task without hesitation

I have much hesitation	A fair amount of hesitation	A good part of it without hesitation	Almost completely without hesitation	Absolutely no hesitation
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

14. My performance would convince an observer that I'm competent at this task

Not at all	Agree, a little	For much of it	For almost all of it	For absolutely all of it
<input type="radio"/>				

15. I feel sure of myself as I perform this task

Not at all	Very little	For much of it	For almost all of it	For absolutely all of it
<input type="radio"/>				

16. I feel satisfied with my performance

Not at all	Very little	For much of it	For almost all of it	For absolutely all of it
<input type="radio"/>				

APPENDIX D

PERMISSION TO USE CONFIDENCE SCALE

WOLTERS KLUWER HEALTH, INC. LICENSE
TERMS AND CONDITIONS

Aug 26, 2019

This Agreement between Ms. Janice Lew -- Janice Lew ("You") and Wolters Kluwer Health, Inc. ("Wolters Kluwer Health, Inc.") consists of your license details and the terms and conditions provided by Wolters Kluwer Health, Inc. and Copyright Clearance Center.

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Portion	Figures/table/illustration
Number of figures/tables/illustrations	1
Figures/tables/illustrations used	The C-Scale
Author of this Wolters Kluwer article	No
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APPENDIX E

PATIENT HEALTH QUESTIONNAIRE-9

PATIENT HEALTH QUESTIONNAIRE-9 (PHQ-9)

Over the last 2 weeks, how often have you been bothered by any of the following problems?
(Use "✓" to indicate your answer)

	Not at all	Several days	More than half the days	Nearly every day
1. Little interest or pleasure in doing things	0	1	2	3
2. Feeling down, depressed, or hopeless	0	1	2	3
3. Trouble falling or staying asleep, or sleeping too much	0	1	2	3
4. Feeling tired or having little energy	0	1	2	3
5. Poor appetite or overeating	0	1	2	3
6. Feeling bad about yourself — or that you are a failure or have let yourself or your family down	0	1	2	3
7. Trouble concentrating on things, such as reading the newspaper or watching television	0	1	2	3
8. Moving or speaking so slowly that other people could have noticed? Or the opposite — being so fidgety or restless that you have been moving around a lot more than usual	0	1	2	3
9. Thoughts that you would be better off dead or of hurting yourself in some way	0	1	2	3

FOR OFFICE CODING 0 + + +
=Total Score:

If you checked off any problems, how difficult have these problems made it for you to do your work, take care of things at home, or get along with other people?

Not difficult at all	Somewhat difficult	Very difficult	Extremely difficult
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

APPENDIX F

MEASUREMENT-BASED CARE DEPRESSION PROTOCOL

Measurement-based Care of Depression Protocol at the St. Joseph Hospital of Orange (Part 1)

*Evidence-based Practice (EBP) sources for algorithm recommendations

**Event=BHS Inpatient admission/discharge PHQ-9 assessment

**Program=BHS outpatient admission/discharge PHQ-9 assessment

Measurement-based Care of Depression Protocol at the St. Joseph Hospital of Orange (Part 2)

(CHART TAB)

Number of MDD Patients by PHQ9 Score Change

